

THE HISTOLOGY OF THE MUSCLE TISSUE

Shodmonova Dilsora Shokirovna

Senior lecturer of Alfraganus University

Orcid Id:0009-0006-2475-8133

Email: shodmonovadilsora7@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10897391>

Introduction

In the realm of human anatomy, there exist three main types of muscles: skeletal, smooth, and cardiac. Skeletal striated muscle stands out as the most prevalent variety, boasting over 400 distinct muscles. It holds the distinction of being the sole muscle type under voluntary control and typically constitutes around 40% of body weight in individuals with a normal body mass index. Smooth muscle, on the other hand, governs the contraction of non-voluntary muscles, playing a multifaceted role in human physiology. It contributes to various organ systems, ranging from regulating vascular resistance to facilitating uterine contractions. Unlike skeletal muscle, smooth muscle functions involuntarily. Cardiac muscle, similar to smooth muscle, operates without voluntary control. What sets cardiac muscle apart is its intrinsic automaticity, which underlies its rhythmic contraction. Despite their cellular differences, all three muscle types share the fundamental purpose of converting chemical energy into mechanical work and facilitating bodily movement.

Structure

In all three types of muscles, individual muscle fibers are arranged in parallel lines to enable contraction, as discussed in the subsequent function section.

Skeletal striated muscles are anchored to bones via dense connective tissue known as tendons. The outermost layer of a muscle is the epimysium, which envelops multiple fascicles that are further encased in perimysium. Each fascicle contains individual muscle fibers surrounded by endomysium. Within these muscle fibers lies the functional unit known as the sarcomere, where cellular contraction occurs. The sarcomere serves as the primary site of muscle activity, with other layers facilitating the tracking of these fibers.

The sarcomere presents as a network of parallel lines, with Z-discs marking the lateral boundaries of each sarcomere. Thin filaments extend from one direction and are anchored to the Z-discs, while thick filaments run in the opposite direction and lie between the thin filaments. The overlap between these filaments forms the foundation of muscle physiology, with increased overlap corresponding to greater muscle contraction.

Smooth muscle lacks the striations characteristic of skeletal muscle and instead exhibits a spindle-shaped morphology. Cardiac muscle, while structurally resembling skeletal muscle with its striations and sarcomeres, possesses unique features due to its automaticity and requirement for synchronization. Intercalated discs facilitate electrical coupling between cardiac muscle cells to ensure coordinated contraction.

Function

Contraction serves to bring the two attachment points of a muscle closer together, thereby generating movement. For instance, consider the sternocleidomastoid muscle, which originates from the manubrium and head of the clavicle and inserts on the ipsilateral mastoid process of the skull. Contraction of this muscle results in ipsilateral side-bending and contralateral rotation, as it functions to bring these bony processes closer together.

The sternocleidomastoid muscle is under voluntary control and thus classified as a striated skeletal muscle. As previously mentioned, the primary mechanism underlying muscle function involves the interaction of thick and thin filaments. The principal proteins constituting these filaments are myosin and actin, respectively. Myosin operates akin to a person climbing a rope, with actin serving as the rope. Myosin binds to actin, undergoes a power stroke (pulling the rope), releases, and then repeats this cycle. Activation of myosin in skeletal muscle cells occurs through a rapid influx of calcium ions released from the sarcoplasmic reticulum, an intracellular store within the muscle cell. Calcium ions bind to troponin, causing a conformational change that displaces tropomyosin from the actin-binding sites, thereby permitting myosin to bind to actin and initiate contraction.

In the absence of calcium, myosin binds to ADP and inorganic phosphate (Pi). When calcium is present, this myosin-ADP-Pi complex binds to actin, forming a cross-bridge. Subsequent release of ADP and Pi triggers the power stroke, during which myosin pulls on actin. ATP then binds to myosin, allowing it to detach from actin. Hydrolysis of ATP into ADP and Pi resets the myosin head, preparing it for another cycle of contraction. Smooth and cardiac muscles employ similar mechanisms for shortening; however, their activation processes differ.

Histochemistry and Cytochemistry

Hematoxylin is a commonly employed staining agent in histology for muscle tissue. It selectively stains nuclei, rendering them blue or purple in color, while eosin serves to stain cytoplasm and extracellular matrix pink. Utilizing this staining technique, one can readily discern muscle fibers and differentiate between the structural characteristics of the three muscle types.

Light Microscopy.

Light microscopy offers a valuable tool for identifying different types of muscle tissues. Skeletal muscle presents as elongated fibers arranged in parallel with numerous perpendicular Z-discs. Smooth muscle exhibits a repetitive fusiform pattern, while cardiac muscle, though visually resembling skeletal muscle to some extent, can be distinguished by the presence of staggered perpendicular lines indicative of intercalated discs. Additionally, cardiac muscle fibers tend to appear more wavy in structure compared to skeletal muscle.

Electron Microscopy

Electron microscopy proves immensely valuable in bridging the gap between physiology and histology, as it provides a level of detail that surpasses what is attainable with light microscopy. The following description offers insight into interpreting an electron microscopy image of striated skeletal muscle.

When examining a sarcomere image, it is crucial to identify its boundaries, delineated by the Z-discs. These lines, perpendicular to the overall fiber, serve as reference points. From there, one can discern distinct regions within the sarcomere. Between two Z-discs, there are seven discernible color changes, rendering the sarcomere symmetric. The areas flanking the Z-discs are referred to as the I-bands, characterized by the presence of thin filaments, hence appearing lighter in grayscale. The remaining five zones constitute the A-band, housing thick filaments. Within the A-band, the H-zone and M-line can be identified. The M-line, situated at the center of the sarcomere, serves as an anchor for the thick filament and exhibits a characteristic color gradient. Adjacent to the M-line are the H-zones, where only thick filaments are present. The darkest region within the A-band, observed in electron microscopy,

signifies the overlap between thin and thick filaments. During muscle contraction, this overlapping area increases in size, while the H-zone and I-band diminish proportionately.

Review from left to right of a sarcomere:

- Z-line – Dark perpendicular line – The sarcomere boundary and anchor for thin filament
- I-band – Lightest – Thin filament alone
- A-band - Thin and Thick filament overlap – Dark area
- A-band - H-zone - Thick filament alone – Second lightest area
- A-band - M-line - Anchoring protein for thick filament – Second darkest line, middle of sarcomere
- A-band - H-zone – Thick filament alone – Second lightest area
- A-band - Thin and Thick filament overlap – Dark area
- I-band – Lightest – Thin filament alone
- Z-line – Dark perpendicular line – The sarcomere boundary and anchor for thin filament

Clinical Significance

Duchenne muscular dystrophy, an X-linked genetic disorder, arises from a mutation in the dystrophin protein, impairing proper muscle contraction. The dystrophin gene, responsible for encoding this protein, ranks among the largest human genes identified to date. Functionally, dystrophin acts as a connector between actin and the extracellular matrix. However, in the absence of this connection, overlapping of actin and myosin filaments fails to elicit contraction. Consequently, repeated contractions lead to cellular death, manifesting clinically with elevated creatinine kinase levels and weakened muscles. Predominantly affecting the lower limbs and posture-related muscles, Duchenne muscular dystrophy presents with characteristic signs such as sway back, weak gluteal muscles, thin thighs, hyper-extended knees (to compensate for upper body load), protuberant abdomen (due to weak rectus abdominis), and impaired balance. A hallmark feature of this condition is calf hypertrophy, which, contrary to visual appearance, stems from chronic necrosis of muscle fibers replaced by fat cells. A related disorder, Becker muscular dystrophy, results from a dystrophin gene mutation but typically exhibits less severe symptoms.

Troponin, a key component involved in calcium-mediated muscle contraction, is also present in cardiac tissue. In cases of significant myocardial damage, such as during myocardial infarctions, troponin is released from cardiac cells, serving as a valuable biomarker for diagnosis.

Rigor mortis, characterized by the hyper-contracted state of muscles post-mortem, may seem paradoxical in the absence of oxygen delivery. However, this phenomenon aligns with the physiological processes described in the function section. In the absence of ATP, required for myosin detachment from actin, myosin remains in a contracted state. Only upon ATP binding can myosin release actin, allowing muscle relaxation.

References:

1. Shadrin IY, Khodabukus A, Bursac N. Striated muscle function, regeneration, and repair. Cell Mol Life Sci. 2016 Nov;73(22):4175-4202. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

2. Brozovich FV, Nicholson CJ, Degen CV, Gao YZ, Aggarwal M, Morgan KG. Mechanisms of Vascular Smooth Muscle Contraction and the Basis for Pharmacologic Treatment of Smooth Muscle Disorders. *Pharmacol Rev.* 2016 Apr;68(2):476-532. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
3. Jafri MS. Models of excitation-contraction coupling in cardiac ventricular myocytes. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2012;910:309-35. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
4. McLoon LK, Vicente A, Fitzpatrick KR, Lindström M, Pedrosa Domellöf F. Composition, Architecture, and Functional Implications of the Connective Tissue Network of the Extraocular Muscles. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 2018 Jan 01;59(1):322-329. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
5. Henderson CA, Gomez CG, Novak SM, Mi-Mi L, Gregorio CC. Overview of the Muscle Cytoskeleton. *Compr Physiol.* 2017 Jun 18;7(3):891-944. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
6. Sieck GC, Ferreira LF, Reid MB, Mantilla CB. Mechanical properties of respiratory muscles. *Compr Physiol.* 2013 Oct;3(4):1553-67. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
7. Birnkrant DJ, Bushby K, Bann CM, Apkon SD, Blackwell A, Brumbaugh D, Case LE, Clemens PR, Hadjiyannakis S, Pandya S, Street N, Tomezsko J, Wagner KR, Ward LM, Weber DR., DMD Care Considerations Working Group. Diagnosis and management of Duchenne muscular dystrophy, part 1: diagnosis, and neuromuscular, rehabilitation, endocrine, and gastrointestinal and nutritional management. *Lancet Neurol.* 2018 Mar;17(3):251-267. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
8. Banks GB, Combs AC, Odom GL, Bloch RJ, Chamberlain JS. Muscle structure influences utrophin expression in mdx mice. *PLoS Genet.* 2014 Jun;10(6):e1004431. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
9. Goldstein SA, Newby LK, Cyr DD, Neely M, Lüscher TF, Brown EB, White HD, Ohman EM, Roe MT, Hamm CW. Relationship Between Peak Troponin Values and Long-Term Ischemic Events Among Medically Managed Patients With Acute Coronary Syndromes. *J Am Heart Assoc.* 2017 Apr 11;6(4) [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
10. Eakins F, Harford JJ, Knupp C, Roessle M, Squire JM. Different Myosin Head Conformations in Bony Fish Muscles Put into Rigor at Different Sarcomere Lengths. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2018 Jul 18;19(7) [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]